

FARMERS PERCEPTION TOWARDS PADDY VARIETIES OF KEDAR SEEDS COMPANY IN BHANDARA DISTRICT

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Abstract

This study examines the market share of Kedar Seeds Company and farmers' perceptions of its paddy varieties in Bhandara district, Maharashtra. Based on surveys of 60 farmers, results show that while most farmers are satisfied with yield quantity and grain quality, concerns remain regarding disease resistance and drought tolerance. Kedar Seeds holds a 14.45% market share locally. The study highlights the need for improved seed resilience and farmer support to enhance adoption and productivity.

Keywords - Kedar Seeds, paddy varieties, adoption and productivity.

Introduction

Seeds are the foundation of agricultural production, directly influencing both the quantity and quality of crops. Over time, the seed industry has advanced significantly due to technological innovations, improved breeding techniques, and a focus on high-yielding, disease-resistant varieties. In India, agriculture remains a major livelihood source, where quality seeds play a crucial role in supporting productivity and food security.

Kedar Seeds Company, established in 2020 in Bhandara district of Maharashtra, is one of the key players in the production and distribution of paddy seeds. The company focuses on providing improved paddy varieties like Shri Lekha, Shri Vitthal, K.S. Raja, and K.S. Gold, which cater to local farming needs. With modern research facilities and a strong distribution network, Kedar Seeds aims to enhance agricultural output by supplying farmers with high-quality, climate-resilient seeds.

Objectives:

1. To study the market share of Kedar Seeds Company.
2. To study the farmers perception of paddy varieties of Kedar Seeds Company.
3. To identify the advantages for adoption of paddy varieties of Kedar Seeds Company.

Methodology:

The study adopted a structured research approach involving data collection through surveys and interviews. Sampling techniques were applied to select farmers from Bhandara district. The research aimed to analyze the market share of Kedar Seeds Company, understand farmers' perceptions of its paddy varieties, and identify reasons for their adoption. Data analysis included evaluation of demographic characteristics, product-specific factors, farmers' knowledge and satisfaction levels.

3.1 Area of study:

The present study of paddy varieties of Kedar Seeds Company was conducted at Bhandara District of Maharashtra state.

3.2 Period of study:

The data had been collected for the period of financial year 2024-2025

3.3 Sampling technique:

Present study was conducted for Bhandara district Two talukas of Bhandara district was purposively selected namely Pauni and Lakhandur. Also from each taluka two villages were selected, from each village 15 farmers and 10 dealers from each taluka was selected. In all total 60 farmers and 20 dealers was selected for present study.

3.4 Source of data:**3.4.1 Primary data:**

The primary data was collected from farmers and dealers through specially design schedule.

3.4.2 Secondary data:

Secondary data was collected from Kedar Seeds Company published report and organised programmes.

3.5. Product selection :

The four paddy varieties of Kedar Seeds Company were selected for the present study namely Shri Lekha, Shri Vitthal, K.S. Gold and K.S. Raja.

3.6. Analytical tool:**Market share of Kedar Seeds Company in Bhandara District :**

To find the market share of Kedar Seeds Company in district it will be calculated with the help of formula as given below:

Selected paddy varieties of Kedar Seeds

$$\text{Market share} = \frac{\text{Selected paddy varieties of Kedar Seeds}}{\text{Total no. of others paddy varieties}} \times 100$$

Total no. of others paddy varieties

3.6.2. To evaluate the farmers perception of paddy varieties of Kedar Seeds Company:

It can be analyses by means of some variables:

1.Demographic variables:

- a)Age-** older farmers might have different perception due to experience or traditional methods, while younger open to modern products.
- b)Education-**Higher education levels may correlate with better understanding of product benefits and risks.
- c)Farm size-**Small scale farmers may have different needs and perceptions compared to larger-scale farmers.
- d)Income Level-**Economic status can affect a farmer's ability to afford or prioritize certain products.

2.Cognitive Variables (Knowledge and Attitudes):

a)Perceived value for money- Farmers' perception of the product's cost relative to its benefits.

3.Behavioral Variables (Usage Patterns and Intentions):

a) Frequency of use - How often do farmers use paddy varieties of Kedar Seeds Company.

3.6.3. Likert scale:

A Likert scale is a rating scale which is used to measure opinions, attitudes or behaviours. It consists of a statement or a question, followed by a series of five or seven answer statements. Respondents choose the option that best corresponds with how they feel about the statement or question. For the evaluation of farmers perception, the following options were used:

1. Excellent
2. Good
3. Average
4. Below Average
5. Poor

Similarly for advantages of seed adoption following rating was used:

1. Strongly agreed
2. Agree
3. Neutral
4. Disagree
- 5.Strongly disagree

Each statement was tasted statistically of its mean score. Further these statements were ranked according to their mean score.

Product- Specific Factors:

Availability: Whether paddy varieties of Kedar Seeds are readily available in local markets or agricultural supply stores.

General Satisfaction:

Overall satisfaction: Farmers general satisfaction with Kedar Seeds Company based on their experience and the outcomes from usage.

The advantages for adoption of paddy varieties of Kedar Seeds Company.

The advantages for adoption of paddy varieties of Kedar Seeds Company were analysed by simple tabular analysis.

Results and Discussion

Table 1. Market share of different Seeds Company.

Sr. No.	Brand Name	Quantity Supply (in Kg)	Price Per Packet (10 Kgs)
1	Mahagujrat Seeds	121580 (27.89%)	718.18
2	Kedar Seeds	63026 (14.45%)	815.71
3	R.J. Bioseeds	61100 (14.01%)	836.36
4	SRS Ganga Seeds	60420 (13.86%)	805.71
5	Paturu	56680 (13.00%)	937.69
6	Ankur Seeds	39700 (9.10%)	947
7	Nuziveedu	33550 (7.69%)	950
	TOTAL	436056	

Note: Based on primary data collected from Dealers

The table 1 shows the market share percentages of various seed companies operating in pauni and lakhandur talukas of Bhandara district. Mahagujrat Seeds holds the highest market share with 27.89%, followed by Kedar Seeds at 14.45% and R.J. Bioseeds at 14.01%. SRS Ganga Seeds accounts for 13.86% of the market, while Paturu holds 13.00%. Ankur Seeds has a market share of 9.10%, and Nuziveedu contributes 7.69%. Altogether, these seven companies represent 100% of the total seed market in the bhandara district.

Market share of Different Companies

Figure 1. Market share of different Seeds Companies in Pauni and Lakhandur talukas of Bhandara District.

Table 2. Demographic Details of Farmers

Sr. No.	Category	Sub-Category	No. of Farmers (n=60)	Percentage (%)
1	Age Group	Below 30	9	15.00
		31-40	14	23.33
		41-50	23	38.34
		Above 50	14	23.33
2	Gender	Male	59	98.34
		Female	1	1.66
		Other	0	0
3	Landholding Size (ha)	Marginal (<1 ha)	23	38.33
		Small (1-2 ha)	12	20.00
		Small-Medium (2-4 ha)	12	20.00
		Medium (4-10 ha)	10	16.66
		Large (>10 ha)	3	5.00
4	Farming Experience (Years)	5-10 Years	12	20.00
		11-20 Years	21	35.00

		>20 Years	27	45.00
5	Education Level	Illiterate	6	10.00
		Primary	24	40.00
		Secondary	28	46.67
		Higher Secondary / Graduate	2	3.33
6	Annual Income (INR)	Less than 50,000	27	45.00
		50,000 - 1,00,000	17	28.34
		1,00,001 - 2,00,000	15	25.00
		Above 2,00,000	1	1.66

The table 2 presents the combined profile of 60 farmers. Most farmers (38.34%) are aged 41-50 years, with males dominating (98.34%). Regarding landholding, 38.33% are marginal farmers with less than 1 hectare of land. Farming experience shows that 45% have over 20 years of experience, indicating a mature farming population. In terms

of education, 46.67% have secondary education, while 10% are illiterate. Income-wise, 45% of farmers earn less than Rs 50,000 annually, showing that most farmers fall under lower-income categories.

Table 3. Overall Farmers Perception towards Paddy varieties of Kedar Seeds Company

Parameter	No. of Respondent	Excellent	Good	Average	Below Average	Poor	Total	Mean Score	Rank based on mean score
		1	2	3	4	5			
Yield Quantity	60	28	25	7	0	0	99	1.65	I
Yield Quality	60	14	26	17	3	0	117	1.95	III
Disease Resistance	60	0	3	23	23	11	222	3.70	IV
Drought Tolerance	60	0	0	13	24	23	250	4.17	V
Grain Quality (Size, Taste)	60	20	25	15	0	0	115	1.92	II

Table 3 summarizes the overall perception of 60 farmers towards the paddy varieties of Kedar Seeds Company using five key parameters. The parameter yield quantity emerged as the most positively rated aspect, with a mean score of 1.65, securing the first rank. Out of 60 farmers, 28 rated it Excellent and 25 rated it Good, reflecting a high level of satisfaction with the productivity offered by these seed varieties.

The second highest-rated parameter was Grain Quality (Size, Taste), with a mean score of 1.92. A total of 20 farmers rated it Excellent, 25 rated it Good, and 15 rated it Average, which shows positive reception regarding the physical and sensory attributes of the grain produced. The parameter Yield Quality received a mean score of 1.95, ranking it third. Among respondents, 14 gave an Excellent rating and 26 rated it Good, indicating that most farmers are generally satisfied with the output quality of the harvested grain.

In contrast, the parameter disease resistance recorded a mean score of 3.70, ranking it fourth. Only 8 farmers rated it Good, while 23 rated it Average, and 34 (23 + 11) rated it either Below Average or Poor. This indicates that a considerable number of farmers experience problems with pest or disease vulnerability in the crops.

The least favorable parameter was drought tolerance, which had the highest mean score of 4.17, ranking it fifth. None of the farmers rated it Excellent or Good. Instead, 13 rated it Average, and 47 (24 + 23) rated it Below Average or Poor. This clearly highlights the variety's weakness in water-scarce or dry conditions.

In conclusion, farmers show strong satisfaction with yield quantity, yield quality, and grain quality from Kedar Seeds paddy varieties. However, concerns remain about disease resistance and especially drought tolerance. These are key areas for improvement to enhance the resilience and performance of these seed varieties across diverse farming conditions.

Table 4. Advantages of Kedar Seeds Varieties

Parameter	No. of respondent	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Total	Mean score	Rank based on mean score
		1	2	3	4	5			
Good germination rate	60	14	31	14	1	0	122	2.03	II
Higher yield	60	14	34	11	0	1	120	2	I
Pest resistance	60	0	0	0	29	31	271	4.51	IV
Low input cost	60	0	13	0	20	27	241	4.01	III

Table 4 presents farmers' perception regarding the advantages of adopting paddy varieties of Kedar Seeds Company. The responses were collected from 60 farmers, and a 5-point Likert scale was used, where 1 = Strongly Agree and 5 = Strongly Disagree. A lower mean score reflects a more favorable perception of the parameter.

For the parameter "Higher Yield," out of 60 farmers, 14 strongly agreed and 34 agreed that Kedar Seeds varieties provide higher yield. Only 1 farmer disagreed, and no one strongly disagreed. This parameter received a mean score of 2.00, securing the 1st rank, indicating that the majority of farmers recognized higher yield as the most important advantage.

Regarding "Good Germination Rate," 14 farmers strongly agreed, 31 agreed, and 14 remained neutral about the parameter, while only 1 farmer disagreed and none strongly disagreed. This parameter received a mean score of 2.033, ranking second, reflecting a positive perception towards seed germination performance.

The parameter "Low Input Cost" received mixed responses. Out of 60 farmers, only 13 agreed, while 20 disagreed and 27 strongly disagreed. This led to a high mean score of 4.016 and a rank of III, suggesting that many farmers do not consider Kedar Seeds economically low-cost in terms of input expenses.

Finally, "Pest Resistance" showed the least favorable response. None of the 60 farmers strongly agreed or agreed. In fact, 29 farmers disagreed and 31 strongly disagreed, giving this parameter a high mean score of 4.516 and the lowest rank (IV). This highlights that farmers are largely dissatisfied with the pest resistance offered by the seeds, making it a critical area for improvement.

5. Conclusion

Kedar Seeds Company holds a significant market share in Bhandara district due to its focus on quality paddy varieties like Shri Lekha and K.S. Raja. Most farmers are satisfied with seed yield, quality, and grain characteristics. However, challenges like poor drought tolerance and disease resistance were identified. Improving these aspects can enhance farmer satisfaction and seed adoption further. Overall, Kedar Seeds plays an important role in supporting regional rice production.

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